

EFFECTIVENESS: ACCEPTANCE AND COMMITMENT THERAPY (ACT) IN ACCEPTING AND MANAGING AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR

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Abstract

Introduction: Aggressive behavior is a change in perception towards stimuli, both internal and external, accompanied by responses that are diminished, excessive, or distorted, either verbally or non-verbally. Aggressive behavior is exhibited by someone with a mental disorder with the intention of attacking either physically or mentally. The provision of nursing interventions is necessary to help patients regain orientation and improve their quality of life. Objective: This study aims to identify interventions that can be used to help patients manage aggressive behavior and how to address it. Method: This study uses a rapid literature review approach utilizing 6 databases, namely PubMed, Sage Journals, Scopus, ScienceDirect, Springer, and EBSCO. with the keywords used "Psychiatric disorders" OR "Mental disorders" AND "Acceptance and commitment therapy" OR "Acceptance based behavioral therapy" AND "Managing aggression," resulting in 8 articles that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Results: Based on the literature review conducted, there are 8 articles with interventions that can be used to reduce aggressive behavior in patients with mental disorders. Conclusion: The results of the literature review have proven that the 8 articles with interventions can reduce aggressive behavior in patients with mental disorders. Therefore, it is recommended that nurses use these interventions to reduce aggressive behavior in patients.

Keywords: Acceptance and Commitment Therapy, Intervention, Aggressive Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mental disorders are a significant global health issue. Mental disorders are syndromes of an individual's behavioral patterns that are typically associated with symptoms of distress or impairment in one or more important human functions, namely psychological, behavioral, biological, and disturbance functions. (Palupi, D. N., Ririanty, M., & Nafikadini, I, 2019). According to Indonesian Law No. 18 of 2014, individuals with mental disorders are those who experience disturbances in thoughts, behaviors, and feelings manifested in the form of a set of symptoms and significant behavioral changes, which can cause suffering and obstacles in fulfilling their functions as human beings (Palupi, D. N., Ririanty, M., & Nafikadini, I, 2019). Behavioral patterns of mental disorders that clinically occur in individuals are associated with distress or disability or accompanied by a significant increase in the risk of death, illness, disability, or loss of freedom (Azhari, N. K., & Anggarawati, T., 2023). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), one in four people worldwide will experience a mental or neurological disorder at some point in their lives. The high prevalence and significant impact on the quality of life of sufferers make mental disorders an important issue that needs to be addressed seriously (Florensa et al., 2023).

The World Health Organization (WHO) in 2013 recorded the number of people with mental disorders worldwide reaching 450 million, and in 2016, WHO data showed that there were around 35 million people affected by depression, 60 million by bipolar disorder, 21 million by schizophrenia, and 47.5 million by dementia. The highest number of mental health disorder patients in Indonesia is found in the DKI Jakarta province (24.3%), Nanggroe Aceh Darussalam (18.5%), West Sumatra (17.7%), NTB (10.9%), South Sumatra (9.2%), and Central Java (6.8%) (WHO, 2023). People with mental disorders experience disturbances within themselves.

Cognitive disorders, attention disorders, memory disorders, associative disorders, thought disorders, consciousness disorders, volition disorders, psychomotor disorders, behavioral disorders, emotional and affective disorders (Azhari, N. K., & Anggarawati, T., 2023). In individuals with mental disorders, emotional and affective disturbances often lead to aggressive behavior. Aggressive behavior emerges when the given stressor to someone cannot control the stressor (Syamsudin, A., Yusuf, A., & Mundakir, 2020). Aggressive behavior is one of the issues in mental disorders. Aggressive behavior itself is a response to anger, disappointment, feelings of revenge, or a threat that causes rage, which can provoke violent behavior as a means of resistance, whether in the form of assault, vandalism, or even murder (Azhari, N. K., & Anggarawati, T., 2023). Aggressive behavior is one of the responses to the stressors faced by an individual. This response can cause harm to oneself, others, and the environment. Considering the impact of the losses caused, the handling of patients with aggressive behavior needs to be carried out quickly and accurately by professional staff, especially nurses (Syamsudin, A., Yusuf, A., & Mundakir, 2020). The role of nurses as providers of nursing care is crucial in handling patients with aggressive behavior. The nursing actions provided to clients with mental disorders will be more comprehensive when combined with psychosocial/specialist therapy, resulting in better outcomes. Psychotherapy that has been applied to clients with mental disorders includes CBT, AT, REBT, RECBT (Susilowati et al, 2014). Several studies conducted show that using nursing therapy is capable of addressing mental disorders with a risk of violent behavior, especially with the use of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), which can lead to aggressive behavior in patients with such diagnoses (Pardede et al, 2015).

ACT helps individuals reduce their suffering by enhancing their awareness and ability to pursue what they desire in life (Sulistiowati, N. M. D., et al, 2014). ACT aims to create a life rich in meaning by accepting all the pain that comes with it. The reduction of symptoms is considered a byproduct or side effect and not the main focus compared to improving the client's quality of life. This therapy changes the client's relationship with complex thoughts and feelings that experienced all this time and taught to perceive those thoughts and feelings as something non-threatening (Elita et al, 2017).

2. METHODOLOGY

This Evidence Based Practice (EBP) uses a rapid literature review design for the quick and systematic collection and analysis of scientific evidence while maintaining the integrity and validity of the results. This rapid literature review is used to compile a synthesis of existing evidence with a focus on relevant articles within a specified timeframe. The review process includes a structured literature search, selection of articles based on specific criteria, and rapid analysis and synthesis of results to produce evidence-based recommendations. The result of this rapid review is an evaluation of the Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) intervention in managing aggressive behavior in patients with mental disorders.

3. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Article searches were conducted systematically according to the 2020 PRISMA Flow Diagram using six databases: Pubmed, Sage Journals, Sciencedirect, Springer, Ebsco, and Google Scholar. The appropriate literature search was conducted using the PICO technique, which stands for P (Population), I (Intervention), C (Comparison), O (Outcome). The population in this literature review is psychiatric disorders or patients with mental disorders with the intervention of acceptance and commitment therapy, and there is no comparison, and the outcome in this study is managing aggression. The articles obtained were then screened to select those that matched the topic of the rapid evidence review being conducted. Articles were screened according to the established inclusion and exclusion criteria. The established inclusion criteria are articles that discuss acceptance and commitment therapy for managing aggression in patients with mental disorders, articles published between 2014 and 2024, articles written in English and Indonesian, availability of full text with free access, and research involving clinical trials, randomized controlled trials (RCT), quasi-experimental studies, and meta-analysis. Meanwhile, the exclusion criteria for article search are articles published before 2014, review articles, non-experimental research articles, and articles not written in English and Indonesian.

Table 1. PICO

Population (P)	Psychiatric disorders
Intervention (I)	Acceptance and commitment therapy
Comparison (C)	-
Outcome (O)	Managing aggression

Figure 1. Prisma

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the 8 identified articles, which consist of national and international articles, a total of 323 respondents participated, with 2 articles from Google Scholar, 2 articles from Pubmed, 1 article from EBSCO, 1 article from Springer, 1 article from Sciencedirect, and 1 article from Sage journal. The results of the research analysis show that each article explains that non-pharmacological interventions for controlling emotions and aggressive behavior include the use of Acceptance Commitment Therapy (ACT), which can be applied through unique and creative approaches to change a person's behavior.

Tabel 2. Ekstrak Data

No.	Title & Author	Country	Goal	Method	Sample	Intervention	Result
1.	Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) for Problematic Anger : A Case Study Penulis : Tiff, E. D., Roberts, M. Z., Underwood, S. B., & Forsyth, J. P. (2022).	Amerika Serikat	Knowing the effectiveness of ACT therapy in controlling anger	Case study	Sample: Mr. R (33 years old), came to the clinic university due to outbursts of anger because he often expresses his anger at work, resulting in verbal arguments with boyfriend and coworker, including throwing equipment or hitting a tree	current awareness, and fostering full acceptance of attention in order to lead a meaningful life. Mr. Ripanta's progress through quantitative and qualitative assessments. The quantitative aspect is measured using a questionnaire: 1. The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II (AAQ-II) 2. The Cognitive Fusion Cuestionario (CFQ) 3. The Difficulties in Emotion Regulation	Overall, quantitative measurements with the AAQ-II, CFQ, DERS, OASIS, ODSIS, and OAngSIS questionnaires, Mr. R shows a successful treatment response marked by a decrease in pre- and post-treatment questionnaire scores. Overall, the treatment benefits observed in quantitative and qualitative assessments showing that Mr. R benefited from ACT for his problematic anger and improved his quality of life.

						Scale (DERS) 4. The Overall Depression Severity and Impairment Scale (ODSIS) 3. The Overall Anger Severity and Impairment Scale (OAngSIS)	
2	trauma: Improvement in psychiatric symptoms, emotion regulation, and treatment compliance following a brief group intervention Penulis : Spidel A., Lecomte T., Kealy D., Daigneault I. (2018).	Canada	in reducing psychological symptoms, controlling emotions, trauma-related symptoms, and improving medication adherence	Quasy eksperimental	50 participants who meet the inclusion criteria Recruited and Randomized to participate in 8 ACT group sessions, or Treatment As Usual (TAU).	ACT combined with mindfulness meditation and usual care (ACT group = 30 people) while the second group only received usual care during the study (TAU group = 20 people). Each ACT group consisted of eight participants, receiving eight sessions lasting 70–75 minutes.	The findings from this study provide evidence that the ACT given in the format the group can be beneficial for those experiencing psychosis and childhood trauma. Participants in the ACT group were found to have improvements in questionnaire scores regarding the overall severity of symptoms, anxiety symptoms, and acceptance of emotional

							regulation abilities. In terms of emotion regulation, this study found that those in the ACT group showed a significant increase in the use of acceptance as an emotion regulation strategy, compared to the TAU group. Additionally, it was found to improve the domain of seeking help from service engagement, thereby potentially contributing to overall patient adherence to mental health care.
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3	Investigati on the effect ofAccepta nce and Commitme nt Therap (ACT) training on stigma and family functionin in family members of patients with psychiatric disorders: randomize d controlled clinical trial Penulis: Afsaneh Parvin., Azizallah Dehghan., Afsaneh Masoumi., Fatemeh Zeraatpish e., Leila Ghaed., Mostafa Bijani. (2024	Iran	This study examines the effects of Acceptanc e and Commitme nt Therapy (ACT) on stigma and family functioning. family members of patients with mental illness, demonstrat e effectivene ss in improving family functioning and coping strategies in dealing with mental illness	Randomiz ed controlled clinical trial	Forty family members of patients with psychiatric disorders	Therapeutic interventions, such as education, support, and psychotherapy can significantly reduce depression, anxiety, and stress in family caregivers, paving the way for improve the quality of care for patients in the family environment. One of the therapeutic approaches that has emerged as part of the third wave of cognitive behavioral therapy is ACT. ACT focuses on two main principles: accepting thoughts and committing to changing	The findings of this article's research indicate that ACT is effective in reducing stigma and improving family functioning in patients with mental disorders. Based on these findings, it is recommended that counselors in psychiatric service centers combine this therapeutic approach with other treatment methods to improve family functioning. , reduce stigma, and address other psychological issues faced by the patient's family
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						<p>behaviors that align with one's values. The main goal is to cultivate psychological flexibility while accepting suffering in life, which ultimately enables individuals to have a richer and more meaningful life. ACT uses various techniques to enhance psychological flexibility. ACT intervention in eight sessions weekly, each lasting 90 minutes, assessed at three time points: before the intervention, after intervention, and during the one-month</p>	
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						<p>follow-up period.</p> <p>Data collection instruments include demographic information questionnaires, stigma assessments, and family functioning measures.</p> <p>family, and family functioning measures</p>	
4	<p>A randomized controlled trial of acceptance and commitment therapy for aggressive behavior</p> <p>Penulis: Ami Zarlg, Erika Lawrence, dan James Marchman</p>	<p>Amerika Serikat</p>	<p>The purpose of the research is to test the effectiveness of the intervention.</p> <p>Acceptance</p>	<p>Randomized controlled clinical trial</p>	<p>Sample of 100 participants</p> <p>Sample criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 2 aggressive actions physical to current partner or ex-partner in the last 6 months. - The group in the same treatment condition in terms of session duration and frequency (12 	<p>The intervention consists of 12 weekly sessions lasting 2 hours per session with 8 - 10 participants and 2 facilitators. Assessment is conducted before treatment, during treatment, after treatment, 3 and 6 months after treatment</p>	<p>The results of the growth curve model analysis show that participants in the ACT group experienced a significant decrease in psychological and physical aggression from before to after treatment and from before treatment to follow-up. Then, the results of the 6-month treatment partially involved</p>

					<p>weekly sessions lasting 2 hours with 8 - 10 members and 2 facilitators) for ensuring parallel therapy contact and the level of exposure to other participants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can communicate in English. - Willing to participate in receiving ACT or control conditions support and discussion. - Age below 18 years not included 	<p>to measuring psychological aggression using the Multidimensional Measure Emotional Abuse Scale (MMEA), physical aggression using the Conflict Tactics Scales (CTS-2), experience avoidance using Avoidance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ), and emotional dysregulation using the Difficulties in Emotion Regulation Scale (DERS)</p> <p>The ACT conducted by the researcher on the respondents was done once (one</p>	<p>mediation with experience avoidance and emotional dysregulation in the post-treatment phase</p>
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						day) consisting of four sessions using Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for nursing actions on respondents with violent behavior at RSUD Tombulilato.	
5	Reduction of Risk Symptoms of Violent Behavior Through Acceptanc e and Commitme nt Therapy (ACT) at RSUD Tombulilat o Authors: Firmawati, Andi Nur Aina Sudirman, and Rona Febryona (2022)	Indonesi an	The purpose of the research is to determine the influence Acceptanc e and Commitme nt Therapy (ACT) toward the reduction of symptoms with the risk of violent behavior in the Regional	The research design uses a quasi- experime ntal design with a one group pre and posttest	The respondents in the study numbered 18. respondents at RSUD Tombulilato. Sample criteria: - Patients with violent behavior being treated at RSUD Tombulilato - Does not have any physical illnesses	The treatment provided starts from 08:00 to 17:00. with a break time from 12:00 to 1:00 PM. The stages of each session are as follows: 1. In the first session, respondents are invited to identify events, thoughts, and feelings that arise, as well as the impact on their behavior and	From the research results, it was found that there is an influence of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) on the reduction of symptoms with a risk of violent behavior at RSUD Tombulilato. The conclusion of this study found that the average behavior of respondents before ACT was implemented at RSUD Tombulilato was

			Public Hospital Tumbobilato		<p>feelings.</p> <p>2. In the second session, respondents are invited to identify values based on their experiences.</p> <p>3. The third session, respondents were trained to accept events using the chosen values.</p> <p>4. Session four, the respondents were taught to have a commitment to maintaining their adaptive behavior. In this session, respondents were taught to have a commitment to maintain their adaptive behavior, namely the respondents. invited to commit to</p>	<p>1.611 with a standard deviation of 0.50, while the average behavior of respondents after ACT was implemented at RSUD Tombulilato was 1.1667 with a standard deviation of 0.38. The statistical results obtained a p-value of 0.007 ($p < 0.05$).</p>
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						preventing the recurrence of bad behavior	
6	The effectiveness of acceptance and commitment therapy for social anxiety disorder: a randomized clinical trial. <i>Trends in psychiatry and psychotherapy</i> , 42(1), 30–38. https://doi.org/10.1590/2237-6089-2019-0003 Penulis : Khoramnia, S., Bavafa, A., Jaberghaderi, N., Parvizifard, A., Foroughi, A.,	Iran	The purpose of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) in reducing difficulties in emotion regulation in individuals with social anxiety disorder	Randomized Clinical Trial	24 people with social anxiety disorder were randomly divided into two groups, namely the experimental group (12 subjects) and the control group (12 subjects).	The experimental group received 12 therapy sessions with acceptance and commitment therapy, Self-Compassion Scale (SCS), Difficulty in Emotion Regulation Scale (DERS), External Shame Scale (ESS), Social Phobia Inventory (SPIN), and Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II (AAQ-II).	The results of this study indicate that ACT is effective in enhancing psychological flexibility, which is consistent with the findings of this study and previous research. The explanatory factor of these results indicates that acceptance and actions taken in ACT can be considered as the main psychological processes, and it seems that this treatment, considering the history of research, is effective for improving psychological flexibility and reducing the symptoms experienced by people with

	Ahmadi, M., & Amiri, S.						social anxiety disorder. It was also found that ACT emphasizes experiencing problematic emotions rather than trying to change thoughts or reduce emotional levels. It seems that ACT is also effective for emotional issues and changes in emotional levels. The results presented in other studies are consistent with this. In this study, the results show that the experimental group compared to the control group in their ability to effectively reduce difficulty in emotion regulation and its components
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7	The influence of acceptance and commitment therapy on symptoms and the ability of clients with a risk of violent behavior. Authors: Sulistiowati, N. M. D., Keliat, B. A., & Wardani, I. Y.	Indonesia	This research aims to determine the effect of ACT on the symptoms and abilities of clients at risk of violent behavior who are treated at Dr. H. Marzoeki Mahdi Hospital in Bogor.	Quasi Eksperimen <i>Randomized controlled trial</i>	60 people at Dr. H. Marzoeki Mahdi Bogor Mental Hospital	Pre-Post Test With Control Group with Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) intervention	The analysis results for respondents' abilities before and after the ACT intervention showed a significant change in the group receiving ACT therapy, with an improvement in the ability to cope with violent behavior by 55.60%. The average ability of clients before receiving ACT therapy in the intervention group was 56.77 (24.73%), and after the intervention, the average ability of clients increased to 103.47 (80.32%). In the control group before the intervention, the average was ability of 49.43 (15.99%), after the intervention, the average ACT
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							ability of the respondents was 78.27 (50.32%). Job characteristics, ACT cognitive abilities, and ACT affective abilities significantly contribute to reducing symptoms of violent behavior.
8	Efficacy of acceptance and commitment therapy on impulsivity and suicidality among clients with bipolar disorders: a randomized control trial Penulis : Mona Metwally El-Sayed, Eman Sameh	Arab	Evaluating the efficacy and commitment therapy towards inflexibility psychological, impulsivity, and suicidal tendencies among bipolar clients	Quasi Eksperimen <i>Randomized controlled trial</i>	Sample: 30 clients with a DSM-5 bipolar diagnosis, and 30 control group clients Sample criteria: Eligibility criteria specifically established to ensure the suitability of participants for this research. These criteria include the requirement that clients must be at least 18 years old, able to	The ACT intervention will consist of eight sessions delivered over eight weeks, with outcome evaluations at the beginning, study completion, and a two-month follow-up. The flowchart for BD (Bipolar disorder) shows that participants (n=30) received acceptance and commitment	presencia (¿cómo se siente aquí?) Sesión 2: Calmando la impulsividad y los impulsos suicidas Sesión 3: El concepto de aceptación Sesión 4: Conociéndose a uno mismo Sesión 5: Comprendiendo los valores de la auto-clasificación Sesión 6: Mejorando las acciones comprometidas en el logro de metas, construyendo patrones

	Abd Elhay, Samah Mohamed Taha, Mahmoud Abdelwahab Khedr, Feby Saad Attalla Mansour and Ayman Mohamed El-Ashr				communicate coherently and meaningfully, possess reading and writing skills, and not have any long-standing illnesses. for more than 10 years. Their medical records taken and reviewed to confirm the client's eligibility. Outpatient patients who meet the criteria for bipolar disorder type I or II as described in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-V) are selected as research subjects through a	therapy (ACT) commitment (ACT) face-to-face for 8 weeks. Each session lasts for 90 minutes. 1. 5 minutes of mindfulness practice 2. 15 minutes: Review the concepts and previous challenges faced by the BD client. during skills demonstration. 3. 30 minutes: Trained researchers will apply and demonstrate the concept new session through video 4. 30 minutes: Discussing the session's goals and skills with clients and ask them to demonstrate the strategies they learned throughout the	acciones comprometidas desired to enhance psychological flexibility. This therapy helps clients find hope, cultivate a fulfilling life, and learn mindfulness, so it is important and clear that the basic principles of ACT are applied to these clients.
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					<p>random selection process</p> <p>session 5. 10 minutes: homework assignment</p> <p>Phase I: Consists of two sessions, with the first session focusing on the general objectives of the ACT session and the participants' expectations. The second session focuses on psychoeducation; topics about medications, symptoms, and medical history are thoroughly discussed to equip the clients. with important information important that needed to understand Bipolar Disorder.</p>	
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						Stage II: The client attends 6 skill training sessions to learn ACT skills to help the person become more psychologically flexible so that they can act according to their values. Session 1: Learning	
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5. DISCUSSION

Anger is defined as a negative emotion triggered by perceived threat provocation and, if not properly managed, can lead to aggressive behavior, interpersonal problems, and physiological disturbances (Berkout et al., 2019). Inappropriate responses to anger and aggressive behavior can lead to more anger, stress, and functional disturbances (Eifert & Forsyth, 2011). Therefore, aggressive behavior often creates new problems, necessitating psychological intervention.

ACT therapy is effective in reducing physical and verbal aggression, stress, while also increasing acceptance, psychological flexibility, and ethically appropriate behavior (Berkout et al., 2019). This is in line with the research by Firmawati et al. (2022), which shows that ACT has an impact on reducing symptoms associated with the risk of violent behavior. ACT focuses on enhancing psychological flexibility, which enables individuals to better cope with negative thoughts and feelings without getting trapped in them (Ardhani & Nawangsih, 2020). ACT therapy teaches acceptance of events that cause unpleasant thoughts and feelings in order to live a more meaningful life by committing to better behaviors (Sulistiowati et al., 2014). In terms of emotion regulation, research by Spidel et al. (2018) found that respondents who received ACT therapy experienced an overall improvement in symptom severity, including the acceptance of emotion regulation abilities. ACT can also be applied to support families as caregivers in helping to manage the stress and emotional burden that often accompany patient care. Supported by Parvin et al (2024), The research conducted by Zarling et al. (2015) used an intervention consisting of 12 weekly sessions lasting 2 hours per session with 8-10 participants, and then measured psychological aggression using the Multidimensional Measure Emotional Abuse Scale (MMEA), and physical aggression using the Conflict Tactics Scales (CTS-2).

The research conducted by Khoramnia et al (2020) used a 12-session therapy intervention with acceptance and commitment therapy, utilizing the Self-Compassion Scale (SCS), Difficulty in Emotion Regulation Scale (DERS), External Shame Scale (ESS), Social Anxiety Scale (SPIN), and Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ-II). This study shows that ACT is effective in improving psychological flexibility, which is consistent with the results of this study and previous research. The research conducted by Sulistiowati et al (2014) used a Pre-Post Test With Control Group intervention with Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) intervention. The analysis results for the respondents' abilities before and after the ACT intervention showed a significant change in the group receiving ACT therapy, with an improvement in their ability to cope with violent behavior by 55.60%. The research conducted by El-Sayed et al (2021) used an 8-session

ACT intervention delivered over 8 weeks, with outcome evaluations at the beginning, study completion, and follow-up after two months. Overall, the application of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) is effective in managing and controlling emotions, aggressive behavior, violent behavior, and encouraging patients to accept negative feelings or thoughts without overreacting. The success of ACT greatly depends on the client's adherence to the exercises and practices recommended by the therapist. However, a lack of motivation or commitment from the client to follow through with the therapy can hinder its effectiveness. Without consistent involvement, the effectiveness of therapy can diminish. Moreover, not all individuals are suitable for this therapy, especially those with severe mental health issues or significant cognitive impairments. Availability of therapists trained can also be a barrier considering this therapy requires experienced professionals to provide effective interventions. Nurses play an important role in supporting patients' mental health. By helping patients accept and manage negative emotions through this ACT therapy, nurses not only reduce the risk of violence but also improve the quality of life for patients, enhancing the therapeutic relationship between nurses and patients.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the literature review that has been conducted, 8 articles with ACT interventions can be used to reduce aggressive behavior in patients. The intervention involved distraction using a pre-post test to assess the effectiveness of the ACT intervention. The results of the literature review proved that the eight articles with the intervention could reduce aggressive behavior in patients with psychotic issues. Therefore, it is recommended that nurses use the intervention to reduce aggressive behavior in patients.

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